

The Huang-Minlon modification of Wolff-Kishner reduction in rapid and simple way using microwave technology¹

Sarmishtha Chattopadhyay, Sajal Kumar Banerjee and Alok Kumar Mitra*

Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, 92 Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : akmitra@cucc.ernet.in Fax : 91-033-3519755

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A high yielding, simple and fast method for the reduction of various aldehydes and ketones to the respective hydrocarbons following Huang-Minlon modification under microwave irradiation is described.

Various methods² have been developed for reduction of carbonyl group in aldehydes and ketones to the respective methyl and methylene groups. A very well known method is Wolff-Kishner reduction³ where the corresponding hydrazones of aldehydes and ketones are converted to the respective hydrocarbons in the presence of sodium ethoxide at 180–200° for 6–8 h. A variety of modifications⁴ have been introduced for this procedure. Perhaps the most important one is the Huang-Minlon modification⁵, which uses diethylene glycol as the solvent and potassium hydroxide as a base with aldehyde/ketone and hydrazine hydrate, and has been shown to be significantly more efficient for this transformation. Although, Huang-Minlon modification is far better than the original reaction, still it has some experimental lacuna : firstly, a very high temperature (180–200°) is required for several hours, and secondly, removal of water formed is necessary at a certain stage.

In the recent years the use of microwave irradiation in organic reaction is rapidly increasing because of the short reaction time, formation of cleaner products and the operational simplicity. It has been commonly employed as thermal energy source in various organic reactions⁶. The use of domestic microwave oven in this regard is now a well established procedure in MORE⁷ (microwave-induced organic reaction enhancement) chemistry.

In continuation of our ongoing programme⁸ for the application of microwave technology in organic synthesis, we have successfully utilized microwave radiation for rehabilitation of Huang-Minlon reaction in a simple way. Here we report the efficient reduction of various ketones (Table 1) and aldehydes (Table 2) to the respective hydrocarbons using hydrazine hydrate, potassium hydroxide and diethylene glycol in excellent yields at ambient pressure within a few minutes under microwave irradiation. In case of ketones, the intermediate hydrazones are formed *in situ*, which are

Table 1. Microwave-assisted reduction of ketones

Substrate	Product/ (yield, %) ^a	Time of irrad., min. ^b / (power level, W)
3-Benzoyl-propionic acid	4-Phenylbutyric acid (90)	(i) 10 (720) (ii) 15 (840)
Benzophenone	Diphenylmethane (88)	(i) 10 (960) (ii) 20 (1080)
1-Tetralone	1,2,3,4-Tetrahydronaphthalene (82)	(i) 10 (1080) (ii) 20 (1200)
6-Methoxy-1-tetralone	1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-6-methoxy-naphthalene (87)	(i) 10 (1080) (ii) 17 (1200)
7-Methoxy-1-tetralone	1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-7-methoxy-naphthalene (87)	(i) 10 (840) (ii) 10 (1080)
3-(4-Methoxybenzoyl)propionic acid	4-(4-Methoxyphenyl)butyric acid (80)	(i) 7 (1080) (ii) 18 (1200)

^aYield refers to pure isolated compound.

^b(i) Time of final irradiation; (ii) time of final irradiation.

then transformed to the respective hydrocarbons. But, in order to avoid the formation of Cannizzaro products, i.e. corresponding acids and alcohols in strong alkaline condition, the aldehydes are first converted to hydrazones in absence of base, then reduction is carried out in the presence of potassium hydroxide. The yields and time of irradiation for the formation of hydrocarbons on reduction of corresponding ketones and aldehydes are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. One of the advantages of this procedure is that water formed is removed spontaneously during the course of the reaction.

In conclusion, we have demonstrated a practical application of the microwave enhanced reduction of aldehydes and ketones to the respective hydrocarbons in excellent yields in a few minutes.

Table 2. Microwave-assisted reduction of aldehydes

Substrate	Product/ (yield, %) ^a	Time of irrad, min, ^b / (power level, W)
Isovanillin	2-Methoxy-5-methylphenol (88)	(i) 5 (960) (ii) 20 (1080)
Piperonal	3,4-(Methylene-dioxy)toluene (84)	(i) 5 (960) (ii) 15 (1080)
2-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	<i>o</i> -Cresol (90)	(i) 5 (960) (ii) 17 (1080)
3-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	<i>m</i> -Cresol (90)	(i) 10 (840) (ii) 12 (960)
4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	<i>p</i> -Cresol (90)	(i) 5 (960) (ii) 17 (1080)
2,4,5-Trimethoxybenzaldehyde	2,4,5-Trimethoxytoluene (86)	(i) 7 (1080) (ii) 17 (1200)
Anisaldehyde	4-Methylanisole (88)	(i) 5 (960) (ii) 17 (1080)
4-Dimethylamino-benzaldehyde	4-Dimethylamino-toluene (89)	(i) 7 (1200) (ii) 15 (1200)
Benzoyloxyvanillin	4-Benzoyloxy-3-methoxytoluene (89)	(i) 10 (1080) (ii) 17 (1200)
Benzoyloxyisovanillin	3-Benzoyloxy-4-methoxytoluene (90)	(i) 5 (960) (ii) 20 (1080)

^aYield refers to pure isolated compound

^b(i) Time of initial irradiation, (ii) time of final irradiation

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillary on an electrically heated metal block and are uncorrected. IR spectra were run on a Perkin-Elmer FTIR-RXI spectrophotometer and ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker AM 300L FT NMR spectrometer operating at 300 and 75 MHz, respectively. The reactions were carried out in a domestic microwave oven (BPL, BMO-700 T, 1200 W).

General method of reduction :

For ketones : A mixture of the ketone (5.6 mmol), 98% hydrazine hydrate (2 ml), KOH (1.1 g) and diethylene glycol (8 ml) was taken in an Erlenmeyer flask fitted with a funnel as a loose top upon which a round-bottomed flask containing ice was placed to serve as a condenser and irradiated in a microwave oven for 7–10 min under power level of 720–1080 W, then raised to 840–1200 W and further irradiated for a 10–20 min. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with water (7 ml), acidified with 6 N HCl, extracted with ether (3 × 20 ml). The ether layer was washed with

water and brine solution thrice, then dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed to get the reduced products (80–90%). The products were identified with the help of IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy.

For aldehydes : A mixture of the aldehyde (6.6 mmol), 98% hydrazine hydrate (2 ml) and diethylene glycol (8 ml) was taken in an Erlenmeyer flask fitted with a funnel and a round-bottomed flask containing ice and irradiated in a microwave oven for 5–7 min under power level of 960–1080 W and then KOH (1.1 g) was added to it and further irradiated for 15–20 min after raising the power level to 1080–1200 W. The mixture was then cooled, diluted with water (7 ml), acidified with 6 N HCl and extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed successively with water and brine, then dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed to get reduced products (84–92%). The products were identified by IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy.

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